

Synthesis and Studies of Some New Phthal-as-Eins

R. P. CHAMOLI*, S. J. RAI† and P. C. GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, Allahabad University, Allahabad-211 002

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Condensation of two γ -keto acids, *o*-(*p*-methylbenzoyl)benzoic acid and *o*-(*p*-methylbenzoyl)tetrachlorobenzoic acid with phenols gives new series of phthalein dyes. These dyes are substituted phthalides in which central carbon atom is attached to two different rings and hence they have been named as phthal-as-eins, 'as' representing unsymmetry and 'ein' the class of compound (phthal-ein). Absorption maxima of these new compounds have been found comparable to those of true phthaleins.

RING-chain tautomerism is encountered in various groups of compounds, e.g., carbohydrates, alkaloids, steroids and γ -keto acids. It has been generally observed that γ -keto acids exist mainly as lactol or as an equilibrium mixture of ring (II) and chain (I) tautomers². The lactol form (II) gives well crystalline acetyl derivative^{3,4} (III) which still retains cyclic structure. Many reactions of γ -keto acids such as formation of pseudo chlorides (IV)⁵, pseudo esters (V)⁶⁻⁸ etc, have been explained on the basis of cyclization of acids to lactol IR^{7,9}, Raman⁸ and nmr¹⁰ spectra have further confirmed the formation of cyclic isomers.

It has also been reported that ring tautomerism of γ -keto acids¹¹ is further exalted by changing R to larger alkyl or aryl groups. It increases further when hydrogen atoms on carbon atoms α to carboxyl group are also changed to larger alkyl groups or α,β -ethylenic bond¹². In recent years Gupta *et al* reported the preparation of a large number of mixed phthaleins and succineins^{13,20}, by condensing various γ -keto acids with phenols. These workers proposed that γ -keto acids undergo condensation through their lactol form and hence the products possess cyclic lactonic structures. In continuation of this work, the present paper describes the synthesis of some new phthal-as-eins by condensing *o*-(*p*-methylbenzoyl)benzoic acid and *o*-(*p*-methylbenzoyl)tetrachlorobenzoic acid with various phenols.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The absorption maxima (visible) have been measured using Beckman model DU spectrophotometer in absolute ethanol (neutral and alkaline media). IR spectra

were taken in KBr with a Perkin Elmer infracord. NMR spectra were recorded on Varian A-60 spectrophotometer using TMS as internal reference. For tlc, plates coated with alumina G-silica gel G (1 : 1) layers were run in ethyl acetate-methanol-5 N ammonia solution (60 : 30 : 10) and spots were developed with 5% aqueous NaOH.

o-(*p*-Methylbenzoyl)benzoic acid and *o*-(*p*-methylbenzoyl)tetrachlorobenzoic acid were prepared by reported procedure²¹. For preparation of acetyl derivative each acid was refluxed with acetic anhydride in presence of fused sodium acetate. The phenols (phenol, resorcinol, catechol, quinol, phloroglucinol and pyrogallol) were taken in slight excess of molecular proportion over the acid (VI). Conc. sulphuric acid (4-5 drops) was used as condensing agent throughout. Each dye, when tested was found free from sulphur. Analogous to phthaleins²², the condensation is supposed to have taken place as shown in Chart 1.

Chart 1

- (VI-X) $R'_1 = R'_2 = R'_3 = R'_4 = H$ or Cl
 (XI) $R_1 = R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = H$; $R_3 = OH$
 (XII) $R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = H$; $R_1 = R_3 = OH$
 (XIII) $R_3 = R_4 = R_5 = H$; $R_1 = R_2 = OH$
 (XIV) $R_2 = R_3 = R_5 = H$; $R_1 = R_4 = OH$
 (XV) $R_2 = R_4 = H$; $R_1 = R_3 = R_5 = OH$
 (XVI) $R_1 = R_5 = H$; $R_2 = R_3 = R_4 = OH$
 (XVII) $R_2 = R_4 = R_5 = H$; $R_1 = R_3 = OCOCH_3$
 (XVIII) $R_5 = H$; $R_2 = R_4 = Br$; $R_1 = R_3 = OH$

Synthesis of *p*-methylphenyl resorcinol tetrachlorophthal-as-ein (XII; $R'_1 = R'_2 = R'_3 = R'_4 = Cl$): An intimate mixture of acid (VI; $R'_1 = R'_2 = R'_3 = R'_4 = Cl$)

* Present address : Chemistry Department, Government Postgraduate College, Gopeshwar (Chamoli), U. P.

† Chemistry Department, Govt. P. G. College, Gyanpur (Varanasi), U.P.

TABLE 1—PREPARATION AND PROPERTIES OF PHTHAL-AS-EINS (X; R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H) AND TETRACHLOROPHTHAL-AS-EINS (X; R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = Cl), RESPECTIVELY

Name of dye, (P = phthal-as-ein)	Condensation		Appearance microcrystalline. Colour	m. p. °C	Yield %	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)		
	Temp °C	Duration hr				C	H	Cl
XI (*) methylphenyl phenol P	150-160	8	yellowish white	165-166	84	79.96 (79.74)	5.28 (5.06)	
XII <i>p</i> -methylphenyl resorcinol P	130-140	3	yellowish; brown	200-201	67	75.62 (75.90)	4.75 (4.93)	
XIII <i>p</i> -methylphenyl catechol P	125-130	2½	grey	172-173	61	75.71 (75.90)	5.20 (4.93)	
XIV <i>p</i> -methylphenyl quinol P	150-160	2½	brownish black	184-185	47	76.30 (75.90)	5.15 (4.93)	
XV <i>p</i> -methylphenyl phloroglucinol P	150-160	1½	brick red	212-213	60	72.69 (72.41)	4.81 (4.59)	
XVI <i>p</i> -methylphenyl pyrogallol P	130-140	1	dirty yellow	220-221	51	72.68 (72.41)	4.80 (4.59)	
XVII <i>p</i> -methylphenyl diacetylresorcinol P	130-140	3	colourless	115-116	52	77.26 (76.92)	5.01 (4.80)	
XVIII <i>p</i> -methylphenyl dibromoresorcinol P	130-140	1	brownish red	208-209	54	Br, 32.90 (32.65)		31.01 (31.27)
XI (*) <i>p</i> -methylphenyl phenol tetrachloro P	180-190	6	light brown	229-230	47	55.75 (55.50)	2.31 (2.64)	30.60 (30.21)
XIII <i>p</i> -methylphenyl catechol tetrachloro P	210-220	1	grey	180-181	33	53.42 (53.61)	2.79 (2.55)	30.52 (30.21)
XIV <i>p</i> -methylphenyl quinol tetrachloro P	200-210	1	brown	160-161	33	53.40 (53.61)	2.81 (2.55)	29.05 (30.21)
XV <i>p</i> -methylphenyl phloroglucinol tetrachloro P	210-220	2	red brown	245-246	50	52.00 (51.85)	2.23 (2.46)	29.56 (29.21)
XVI <i>p</i> -methylphenyl pyrogallol tetrachloro P	210-220	½	blackish brown	240-241	51	51.64 (51.85)	2.30 (2.46)	29.21 (29.21)
XVII <i>p</i> -methylphenyl diacetylresorcinoltetrachloro P	130-140	4	yellowish white	140-141	68	54.45 (54.15)	2.59 (2.88)	25.42 (25.63)
XVIII <i>p</i> -methylphenyl dibromo resorcinol tetrachloro P	room temp	over night	brick red	260-261	69			Br, 25.86 (25.47)

(*) Excess phenol after condensation was removed by steam distillation.

(7.5 g) and resorcinol (2.0 g) was taken in a hard glass boiling tube and heated in an oil bath to 180°. Conc. sulphuric acid (5 drops) was added to the homogeneous contents and heating was continued between 180-190° for 1 hr to get a hard and brittle mass on cooling. The condensed mass was crushed, washed thoroughly with water to remove excess of resorcinol and extracted with 2% aqueous NaOH. The dye was precipitated from the red pink (green fluorescent) filtrate by adding hydrochloric acid gradually with stirring. The dye was filtered, washed with water and purified by repeated crystallization from rectified spirit, dried in an oven at 110° and finally over P₂O₅ in a vacuum desiccator (yield 6.2 g; 60%).

The dye is yellow microcrystalline solid, m.p. 250-251°. The ethanolic solution is yellow with light green fluorescence which on addition of alkali changes to red-pink with intense green fluorescence. Found: C, 53.80; H, 2.67; Cl, 30.53; Mol. wt. 458 (Rast). Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₂O₄Cl₄; C, 53.61; H, 2.55; Cl, 30.21%; Mol. wt. 470.

Paper chromatography of dyes (XI): On Whatman No. 1 test paper, *n*-butanol-ammonia was allowed to run for 13 hr (descending) to give two pink spots of the dye (XI) and reference dye phenolphthalein. R_f: dye XI (R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = Cl), 0.89; phenolphthalein, 0.91 (lit²³ R_f 0.92).

Acetylation of dyes (XII): The dye (XII; R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = Cl) (1.0 g) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (15.0 ml) and fused sodium acetate (3.0 g) at 130-140° for 4 hr to give yellowish white acetyl derivative (0.80 g), m.p. 140-141° (from acetic acid). Found: C, 54.45; H, 2.59; Cl, 25.42; Acetyl, 15.41. Calcd. for C₂₅H₁₆O₆Cl₄ or C₂₁H₁₀O₄Cl₄(COCH₃)₂; C, 54.15; H, 2.88; Cl, 25.63; Acetyl, 15.16%.

Bromination of dyes (XII): The dye (XII, R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = Cl) (1.0 g) was dissolved in absolute ethanol and bromine (2 ml) was added to it drop by drop with shaking. The contents were left overnight at room temperature. The dibromo compound separated as brick red solid (0.9 g), m.p. 260° (from 80% ethanol). It dissolves in ethanol with pinkish red colour which is intensified on addition of alkali. Found: Br, 25.86. Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₀O₄Cl₄Br₂; Br, 25.47%.

Caustic potash treatment of dyes (XII): The dye (XII: R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = Cl) (1.0 g) was mixed with a paste of caustic potash pellets (10.0 g) in a platinum crucible and heated at about 250° for 3 hr until the pink colour of the dye completely disappeared. The contents were cooled and dissolved in water (50 ml) and filtered. The excess of alkali was just neutralized by dil. HCl when a yellowish brown residue (A) settled down. The residue was filtered

TABLE 2—ABSORPTION MAXIMA OF PHTHAL-AS-EINS (X; R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H) AND TETRACHLOROPHTHAL-AS-EINS (X; R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = Cl), RESPECTIVELY. G. F. = GREEN FLUORESCENCE

Dye	Colour in ethanol		Colour with 2% NaOH	λ _{max} (nm)		
	Neutral	Alkaline		Neutral	at	pH
XI	light yellow	light red	light red	500	530	9.0
XII	yellowish red (G. F.)	red	red	480	500	9.5
XIII	colourless	red	red	—	510	8.5
XIV	yellowish brown	brown	reddish brown	—	—	—
XV	yellow orange	red	red	420	460	9.0
XVI	yellow	brownish red	brownish red	—	—	—
XVII	light yellow	light yellow	light yellow	—	—	—
XVIII	light red	red	red	520	530	10.00
XI	light yellow	pink	pink	500	530	9.5
XII	yellow (light G. F.)	red pink (G.F.)	red pink (G. F.)	490	510	10.00
XIII	yellow	yellow brown	dark yellow brown	—	—	—
XIV	light yellow	light pink	light pink	—	520	9.00
XV	orange	brownish red	brownish red	450	—	—
XVI	yellow brown	green	dark green	—	—	—
XVII	light yellow	light yellow	colourless	—	—	—
XVIII	pinkish red	pinkish red	deep pink	520	530	10.00

TABLE 3—ABSORPTION MAXIMA OF SOME KNOWN PHTHALIEINS

Name of dye	Colour in ethanol		Colour with 2% NaOH	λ _{max} (nm)		
	Neutral	Alkaline		Neutral	at	pH
Phenolphthalein	colourless	pink	pink	—	550	10.5
Fluorescein	yellow red	red (G. F.)	reddish pink (G. F.)	480	500	10.00
Eosin	light pink (G. F.)	orange pink (G. F.)	orange pink (G. F.)	530	530	9.5

and washed with water. The filtrate was further acidified by adding an excess of dil. HCl giving a white residue (B) which was also filtered and washed with water. The filtrate was extracted with ether and on evaporation of excess of solvent a brownish red residue (C) was obtained. Residues A, B and C, were identified as unreacted residual dye (XII), acid (VI) and resorcinol (XIX), respectively by direct comparison (m.m.p, co-tlc, co-ir) with their authentic samples.

Results and Discussion

o-(*p*-Methylbenzoyl)benzoic acid (VI: R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H) and *o*-(*p*-methylbenzoyl)tetrachlorobenzoic acid (VI: R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = Cl) have been found spectroscopically to exist as a mixture of ring and chain tautomers. IR spectra of the acids showed notable absorption bands at 1695-1690, 1670-1660, and 1760 (very feeble) cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of carboxyl >C=O, diaryl ketonic >C=O and lactonic >C=O, respectively. Broad bands at 2700-2640 and 3460-3440 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to -OH of carboxyl and -OH of lactol form of the acids, respectively. The nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) of these two acids showed the presence of a hydroxy proton of the lactol form (a broad singlet of low intensity at τ 4.7 and 4.5).

IR spectra of the acetyl derivatives of the acids showed a peak at 1780 cm⁻¹ due to lactonic >C=O. Other peaks at about 1755, 1235, 1200 and 1000 cm⁻¹ have been ascribed to OCOCH₃ group. Peaks at 2640, 1695-1690, 1670-1660 cm⁻¹ were found absent in the ir spectra of the corresponding acetyl derivatives. NMR spectra of acetyl derivatives did not

contain any signal at τ 4.7 and 4.5 (present in the nmr spectra of the acids), but there was a new signal at τ 7.5 (singlet, 3H) due to OCOCH₃ group.

These spectral studies revealed that the acids are mixture of keto (VI) and lactol (VII) form and formation of acetyl derivatives takes place through the lactol form. Similarly, condensation of acids with phenols also occurs through the lactol form, and with excess of phenols the entire acid taken reacts as

Chart 2

(R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = R₄ = H = Cl)

lactol (VII) (Chart 1). The purity of the dyes has been confirmed by tlc and paper chromatography. The structures have been confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis, bromination, acetylation and KOH degradation studies (Chart 2). Formation of diacetyl derivatives (XVII) and dibromo derivatives (XVIII) support the presence of only one resorcinol molecule in the dyes (XII). KOH fusion of dyes (X I) yielded acids (VI) and resorcinol (XIX).

The absorption maxima of these phthal-as-eins are given in Table 2 and are comparable to those of known phthal-eins prepared in similar manner (Table 3).

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